

Protocol for a Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of a Transitional Care Intervention for Frail Older Adults

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Abstract

Background: Early hospital readmissions among older adults are common and are associated with negative health outcomes and increased healthcare costs. Transitional care interventions (TCI) provide care in the transition between two settings, such as hospital and home. These interventions have shown effectiveness in reducing readmissions, but current evidence of their cost-effectiveness is inconclusive.

Objective: This study aims to assess the cost-effectiveness of an advanced practice nurse–led transitional care intervention for frail older adults transitioning from hospital to home.

Methods: The analysis is embedded within the AdvantAGE study conducted in a Swiss hospital for geriatric medicine. A prospective intervention group receiving a transitional care intervention in addition to usual care will be compared to a historic control group receiving usual care, only. Costs will be measured from the perspective of mandatory health insurers, including both intervention costs and healthcare utilization over 30- and 90-day time horizons, respectively. The readmission rate will be used to measure the intervention's effect. The incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) will be calculated, and sensitivity analyses will evaluate the robustness of results to uncertainties in costs and effects.

Expected Impact: This cost-effectiveness analysis will provide context-specific evidence on the economic value of a TCI in Switzerland, complementing clinical findings and informing decisions on sustainable implementation and financing of transitional care models in the Swiss healthcare system.

Background

Hospital readmissions among the elderly are common and can have substantial consequences for both patients and healthcare systems. Large cohort studies report 30-day readmission rates for older adults of 11.6% after major surgery and up to 20% following acute medical admissions [1, 2], with rates being even higher among older individuals with multiple comorbidities and frailty [3]. Hospitalisations in this population are associated with negative outcomes such as accelerated cognitive decline and loss of independence in activities of daily living [4, 5]. A significant proportion of these readmissions are potentially avoidable, with studies suggesting that over 40% could be prevented [6]. Moreover, avoidable readmissions are associated with high per-case expenditures, as shown in two US studies [7, 8], underscoring the economic value of interventions aimed at preventing them. Reducing unnecessary rehospitalizations is therefore both a clinical and economic priority.

Transitional Care Interventions (TCIs) are an effective approach to reduce readmission rates. They aim to ensure continuity of care and prevent adverse outcomes during transitions between care settings, for example between hospital and home [9]. TCIs are typically delivered by multidisciplinary teams and include interventions such as care coordination, patient and caregiver education, and self-management support [10]. Evidence from multiple studies shows that TCIs can reduce readmissions and improve quality of life and other health outcomes [11]. However, their effectiveness varies depending on implementation and adaptation to local contexts [12] indicating that interventions must be tailored to specific settings.

In Switzerland, chronic diseases are a major driver of hospital admissions and healthcare costs, with inpatient care exceeding those of many other European countries [13]. Here, healthcare financing is shared between mandatory health insurance, cantonal contributions, and out-of-pocket payments by patients. Cost responsibility differs across sectors: inpatient hospital care is reimbursed through the Swiss Diagnosis-Related Groups (DRG) system [14] and jointly funded by insurers and cantons, whereas ambulatory services are predominantly covered by health insurers. The national health strategy *Health 2030* identified fragmented care structures and the rising burden of chronic illness as key challenges, emphasizing the urgent need for integrated and coordinated care models to enhance continuity, quality, and efficiency [15]. TCIs directly support these objectives by improving coordination between hospital and community services and promoting patient-centered care pathways. However, despite their potential, TCIs have not yet been implemented within regular healthcare services in Switzerland.

The AdvantAGE project (“Development and Implementation of an Advanced Practice Nurse-led Interprofessional Transitional Care Model for Frail Geriatric Adults”) addresses this gap by developing, implementing, and evaluating a TCI for frail older adults in Switzerland. The study is conducted at a hospital for acute and rehabilitative geriatric medicine in Switzerland with data collection running from January 2024 to March 2026, evaluating the effect of the TCI on the readmission rate in frail older adults [16]. For the long term implementation of this TCI with sustainable funding, robust evidence on its cost-effectiveness is essential. Several systematic reviews [17-21] have reported inconclusive results for cost-effectiveness of TCIs, primarily due to small sample sizes, partial economic analyses, and high variability in study designs and populations. These issues have led to a lack of generalizable conclusions regarding the cost-effectiveness of TCIs. Furthermore, research on the costs associated with implementing TCIs is sparse and highly context-specific [22, 23], making it difficult to apply findings across different healthcare settings. As a result, current evidence does not provide sufficient guidance for policymakers and healthcare providers looking to adopt and sustain TCIs in practice. To address this gap, more robust studies are needed that provide reliable, contextually relevant data on both the costs and cost-effectiveness of TCIs, enabling a clearer understanding of the resources required for their implementation and long-term sustainability.

This health-economic evaluation is nested within the AdvantAGE study and aims to assess the cost-effectiveness of the AdvantAGE TCI. Given the Swiss healthcare system's reliance on mandatory health insurance, evaluating the economic impact of the AdvantAGE TCI from a health-insurance perspective is crucial for understanding its financial implications. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Describe the costs of the TCI and usual care, including associated inpatient healthcare utilization.
2. Describe the costs of implementation strategies used for the AdvantAGE TCI.
3. Calculate the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of the AdvantAGE TCI compared with usual care, from a health-insurance perspective.

The findings will provide evidence to inform healthcare policy and guide the potential implementation of transitional care models for older adults in Switzerland.

Method

A cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) will be conducted. This protocol follows the CHEERS-guideline [24].

Setting and location: This CEA is nested in the AdvantAGE study with a prospective intervention and historic control group evaluating the effect of a TCI on 30- and 90-day readmission-rates in frail older adults [16]. The AdvantAGE study takes place in the University Department of Geriatric Medicine FELIX PLATTER (UAFP), located in the city of Basel in Switzerland. The UAFP offers acute and rehabilitative care for geriatric patients and treats on average 5000 patients per year.

Study population: Participants for the intervention were recruited at the UAFP between January 2024 and December 2025 in the UAFP. The eligibility criteria for the intervention group are described in Box 1.

The historic control group will be built based on propensity score matching using the data of hospitalized patients between 2019 and 2022 in the UAFP. The sample of the intervention group will include at least 220 individuals, while the sample size of the control group will include at least 660. More information on the rationale for the sample size can be found at the protocol of the AdvantAGE study [16].

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• being a resident of the canton Basel-Stadt;• being able to speak and comprehend German;• planning for discharge to their home;• being aged 65 years or older;• being identified by a clinician as having a high risk of health deterioration due to frailty. <p>In addition, patients must meet at least one of the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• being diagnosed with a complex chronic disease requiring support in self-management and disease management;• facing socially challenging situations such as living alone without a supportive network;• being admitted for an acute illness with a brief hospital stay and needing support in self-and disease management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• being a nursing home resident or having been newly admitted to one;• lack of informal caregivers while exhibiting severe cognitive impairment (Mini Mental Status Examination ≤ 23) (Folstein et al., 1975);• scoring below 50 in the motoric domain of the Functional Independence Measure (Keith et al., 1987);• having a psychiatric disorder that significantly impacts their ability to manage daily life.

Box 1: Eligibility Criteria for the AdvantAGE transitional care intervention

Comparators: The cost-effectiveness analysis will compare usual care (UC) plus the AdvantAGE TCI with UC alone.

Intervention: The TCI consists of five intervention elements: 1) continuous support for patients and caregivers; 2) care coordination with primary care providers; 3) comprehensive health management at home; 4) medication-and self-management with patients and caregivers; and 5) proactive advance care planning. The TCI is conducted by a multidisciplinary team, including Advanced Practice Nurses (APN) (3 Full Time Equivalents (FTE)), geriatricians (0.2 FTEs), social workers (0.5 FTEs), a dietician (0.1 FTEs) and an occupational therapist (0.1 FTEs). APNs lead the transitional care intervention and visit patients at home after their hospital discharge for a maximum of 90 days. During this period, the frequency and duration of home visits are not dictated by a fixed schedule, but rather, are determined

by the individual needs of each patient. In instances where APNs require expanded expertise for the care of their patients, they consult other members of the multidisciplinary AdvantAGE team.

Care as usual: All patients of the UAFP are provided with individualized and coordinated discharge planning, conducted by the hospital's social workers. This includes organizing and coordinating outpatient services based on the patients' specific needs upon returning home. The discharge planning process commences during the patient's stay at the UAFP and concludes with their discharge.

Perspective: This economic evaluation adopts the perspective of mandatory health insurance. Accordingly, the analysis will include costs relevant to health insurers within the Swiss financing system, encompassing both healthcare utilization and intervention-related expenditures.

Time horizon: This CEA will use a 30-day and a 90-day time horizon. The 90-day time horizon corresponds to the duration of the intervention and the trial's follow-up period, ensuring that both cost and effect estimates are based on directly observed data. The 30-day time horizon will focus on costs and effects within the first 30 days, capturing the short-term outcomes and early effects of the intervention. Evidence on the effects of transitional care interventions (TCIs) in frail older adults beyond the intervention period is mixed. While TCIs generally show beneficial effects on readmissions during the intervention period, the duration of observed effects following the intervention time varies, with some studies reporting reductions for one month [25] and others for up to six months [26]. Given the heterogeneous evidence for longer-term effects, the authors reserve the option to conduct a cost-effectiveness analysis over an extended time horizon.

Discount rate: In this study, we will not apply a discount rate on the costs due to the time horizon under one year.

Selection of outcomes: The outcome measures employed for the CEA are readmission rates within 30 and 90 days after discharge. Readmission is defined as all inpatient acute care received without interruption from admission to discharge to a non-acute setting. Examples for readmission may include emergency department visits with subsequent stays on acute wards in different hospitals, or hospitalization in one hospital only. Inpatient rehabilitation stays are not included.

Measurement of effects: The readmissions within the intervention group are documented by AdvantAGE-APNs. Furthermore, we will use data from the UAFP and the cantonal university hospital's patient information systems to identify readmissions in the control group, and to validate the readmissions and their timing in the intervention group.

Measurement and valuation of resources and costs: We will assess both the intervention costs and healthcare utilization costs. For the intervention group (UC + TCI), total costs will include the costs of the intervention and healthcare utilization, whereas for the control group (UC only), costs will include healthcare utilization alone. Healthcare utilization comprises readmissions and Emergency Department (ED)-visits within the specified time horizon. As UC is identical in both groups, these costs will not be included in the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) calculation. Due to the design of the underlying study, certain cost components, such as general practitioner visits and services provided by homecare teams, were not available for the historical control group and will therefore not be included in the analysis. All other relevant costs borne by health insurers will be incorporated. Table 1 lists all cost variables considered in this analysis.

Intervention costs will be measured and valued using a time-driven activity-based costing approach [27]. The AdvantAGE team documents each activity and the corresponding time spent using the hospital-wide accounting system. Recorded times will then be valued using the respective average UAFP salary for each professional group. For physicians, costs will be assigned based on the national outpatient reimbursement tariff system (TARMED) [28]. Overhead costs will be added to the intervention costs and will be based on the actual overhead expenditures allocated to the intervention in the hospital's annual cost extract, including administrative, infrastructure, and service department costs.

For the valuation of healthcare utilization, the SwissDRG assigned to each rehospitalisation and ED-visit will be extracted from the administrative data warehouses of the UAFP and the university hospital.

The cost will be calculated using the respective hospital base rate for each year of rehospitalisation, with inflation adjustments applied accordingly.

Table 1: Overview of CEA-relevant variables including measurement and valuation

Category	Variable	Measurement	Valuation	Data Source	Group
Intervention costs – Personnel	Advanced Practice Nurse (APN), Social Worker, Dietician, Occupational Therapist	Time recorded per activity in hospital accounting system	Average salary per profession (per hour)	UAFP	Intervention
	Physicians	Time recorded per activity in hospital accounting system	Tariff-based price per activity	TARMED [28]	Intervention
Intervention costs – Overhead	Facility costs, infrastructure, IT and communication equipment (computers, phones, bikes), administration (accounting, HR), depreciation	Costs per year	Prices per unit billed by UAFP	UAFP, annual cost extract	Intervention
Healthcare utilization	Readmission	Number of hospital stays within 30 and 90 days	DRG-based reimbursement per stay	Administrative data (UAFP and university hospital), SwissDRG [14]	Intervention, Comparator
	ED visits	Number of ED visits within 30 and 90 days	DRG-based reimbursement per ED-visit	Administrative data (UAFP and university hospital), SwissDRG [14]	Intervention, Comparator

Measurement and valuation of Implementation: The costs of implementing the TCI will be assessed, thus providing decision-makers (e.g., healthcare providers) with a comprehensive understanding of the real-world financial implications associated with adopting the intervention. It is important to note that these costs will not be included in the CEA, as they are not currently covered under the health insurance financing scheme.

Implementation strategies conducted in the course of the AdvantAGE project that are presumed to be essential for others to implement the intervention will be incorporated [16]. Costs of implementation will be estimated based on a time-driven activity based costing approach [27].

Currency, price date, and conversion: All costs will be reported in Swiss francs (CHF). The price year will be specified for each cost component. Depending on data availability, costs will be presented in 2025 or 2026 price levels, with adjustments applied as necessary.

Analysis Plan

The following analysis plan outlines the methods for calculating the cost-effectiveness of the TCI compared with UC. The ICER will be estimated based on 30- and 90-day costs and readmission outcomes derived from the main cohort study. In general, ICERs are calculated as the ratio of the difference in mean costs to the difference in mean outcomes between groups, as shown in figure 1 [29].

$$ICER = \frac{\Delta Costs}{\Delta Outcomes}$$

where

- *ΔCosts equals the difference between costs of intervention and control group.*
- *ΔOutcomes equals the difference between effect measured in the intervention and control group.*

Figure 1: Calculation of ICER of the AdvantAGE TCI

Outcomes: Analyses of the effect of the intervention on 30- and 90-day rehospitalisation will be reported in a separate paper. The resulting effect estimates will inform the CEA. Full details are provided in the protocol of the underlying study [16].

Costs: The arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and 95% confidence intervals of total costs will be calculated for each group.

Cost-effectiveness: We will calculate the ICERs for the 30- and 90-day time horizon (reflecting readmission rates at 30 and 90 days post-discharge) as the ratio of incremental costs to incremental effects based on the estimates from the underlying study [16] and measured costs. Depending on the data, additional regression or resampling methods may be applied to account for correlation between costs and effects. Sensitivity analyses will be conducted to assess the robustness of the 30- and 90-day ICERs with respect to uncertainties in both costs and effects. Where appropriate, exploratory subgroup analyses may be undertaken, e.g., patient subgroups defined by specific clinical characteristics.

Results

We will report baseline characteristics of the intervention and control groups descriptively, including demographic, socio-economic, and clinical variables, to allow assessment of group balance.

Costs:

Total and component costs (implementation, intervention, rehospitalisation, emergency visits) will be summarized for each group. For each cost variable, the arithmetic mean, standard deviation and confidence intervals will be reported. For skewed data, the median and interquartile range will also be provided. Differences in mean costs between groups will be presented with corresponding confidence intervals.

Cost-effectiveness:

Results will include ICERs, expressed as Swiss francs (CHF) per rehospitalisation avoided, for the 30- and 90-day time horizon. ICERs will be illustrated on a cost-effectiveness plane, and uncertainty in the estimates will be presented using cost-effectiveness acceptability curves. In the absence of a formal

willingness-to-pay threshold for avoiding rehospitalisation, a pragmatic reference point for interpreting ICERs will be derived from the average DRG-based costs of readmissions.

Discussion

This CEA will generate evidence on the economic and clinical value of a TCI for older adults in Switzerland, contributing to current knowledge on such interventions.

Two main limitations should be noted. First, the choice of a mandatory health-insurance perspective represents a deviation from commonly recommended standards in economic evaluation, which advocate adopting a healthcare system or societal perspective [30, 31]. Nevertheless, for interventions evaluated in real-world settings, it is common and often appropriate to adopt a narrower perspective, such as that of the payer. In this study, the narrower perspective was selected to maximize decision-making relevance, as coverage and reimbursement decisions for transitional care interventions in Switzerland fall primarily within the remit of health insurers. A key limitation of this approach is that costs borne by patients are not captured. Although out-of-pocket payments for the intervention itself are expected to be minimal, Switzerland has one of the highest household out-of-pocket cost shares among OECD countries, which may contribute to financial burden for some patients [32].

Consequently, while the present analysis provides policy-relevant insights for insurers and payers, future research adopting a broader healthcare system or societal perspective would offer a more comprehensive assessment of the intervention's economic and equity implications.

Second, the analysis excluded potentially relevant costs, such as ambulatory physician visits, medication and homecare services, due to limitations in the available data. However, the respective costs differences between intervention and control group are expected to be negligible and are therefore unlikely to substantially affect the comparison between the intervention and control groups.

Despite these limitations, the planned analysis offers important strengths. The results will potentially provide decision-makers in Switzerland with essential evidence on the economic value of a TCI. By generating context-specific cost and outcome data, this CEA addresses a key requirement for translating research into policy and practice. The findings will therefore serve as an important basis for decisions on whether and how transitional care models can be sustainably implemented and financed within the Swiss healthcare system.

Other relevant information

Source of funding: The AdvantAGE project received funding from the Health Department of the Canton Basel-Stadt for the clinical team, and from the Nursing Science Foundation Switzerland for the scientific evaluation.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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